

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF GRAPH-BASED NOSQL DATABASES

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Abstract

In the introductory part of the paper, a brief historical overview of NoSQL databases, their origin and use, reasons for introduction, advantages and disadvantages, similarities and differences with relational databases will be described. In the next part, the focus of the paper will shift to graph-based NoSQL databases along with the main features and properties of three main categories of NoSQL databases – Neo4j, ArangoDB and OrientDB. Special emphasis will be placed on structure, implementation, examples of graph-based databases and use cases. It is important to single out main representatives of graph-based NoSQL databases, with a more detailed description of functionalities and architecture. All of the previously mentioned aims to present a comparative analysis of the previously described databases according to the given criteria in order to summarize the results of the analysis in the final part of the paper with recommendations and best practices.

Keywords: nosql, graph, Neo4j, ArangoDB, OrientDB

Introduction

The world of computer science is advancing and evolving in line with numerous achievements in the fields of science and technology. Many improvements are taking place in programming languages, architectures, platforms, and processes. However, throughout all this time, one thing has remained constant - relational databases store data. There have been considerable challenges, many of which have found success in certain niches, but overall, the issue of data storage has been a central concern for architects when deciding to use relational databases. There is great value in the stability of this reign. The data that organizations store lasts much longer than the applications themselves, so it is highly valuable to have a stable data repository that is well-understood and accessible from many applications, systems, as well as platforms [1].

SQL (Structured Query Language) databases have been the primary mechanism for storing data for over four and a half decades. The use of these databases exploded in the late 1990s with the rise of web application development and open-source platforms, such as MySQL, PostgreSQL, and SQLite [2].

The digital world is growing rapidly and becoming increasingly complex in terms of volume (from terabytes to petabytes), diversity (structured, unstructured, and hybrid), and speed (high growth rate). For quite some time, relational databases have been the default choice for serious data storage, especially in the realm of business applications. However, in the last two and a half decades, a new "contender" has emerged under the label of NoSQL. It has arisen out of the need to handle larger volumes of data, which has forced a fundamental and significant shift in the development of hardware platforms in the form of servers [1].

NoSQL databases are non-relational data management systems that do not require a fixed schema. The primary purpose of using NoSQL databases is for distributed data storage with vast data storage needs. NoSQL stands for "Not only SQL" or "Not SQL." Carl Strozzi introduced the concept of NoSQL at the end of the last century. Traditional relational database management systems (RDBMS) use SQL syntax for storing and retrieving data for further manipulation. Instead, the NoSQL database system encompasses a wide range of database technologies capable of storing structured, semi-structured, unstructured, and polymorphic data [3].

NoSQL is used for processing large volumes of data and real-time web applications. For instance, companies like X, Facebook, and Google collect terabytes of user data every hour [3].

NoSQL databases have been around for some time, but they have gained prominence in recent years. After a long period of SQL dominance, the current excitement surrounding NoSQL databases comes as a surprise. The main idea is to explore the reasons why relational databases are not as dominant and why many scientists and researchers believe that the emergence of NoSQL databases can never completely replace relational databases.

Problem Description

Graph-based databases are currently attracting significant interest because they can provide useful tools for modeling data that better align with understanding of data operates in the real world. This can enable a high level of flexibility as data can be represented in a way that makes the most sense for all involved parties while simultaneously leveraging complex interactions between them [4].

Before fully understanding of graph-based databases, it is necessary to grasp the concept of graphs. In mentioned context, a graph database represents a mathematical graph. Actually, a graph is simply a collection of elements - typically referred to as nodes (also known as vertices or points) - connected by edges (links). Each node represents some data in the graph, while each edge represents a connection between two nodes. Graphs are already present in the real world and in software development, too. Even everyday internet usage can be represented using a graph. Every computer on the Internet - servers, routers, modems - is

a node, and each connection between them is an edge (connectivity, communication or file and message exchange) [4].

A graph consists of two elements: nodes and relationships (edges). Each node represents an entity (person, place, thing, category, or other data), and each relationship represents the way how two or more nodes are connected. The social network Twitter (recently rebranded as X) is also a perfect example of a graph database, connecting more than 330 million active users [5].

Pic. 1. Twitter users represented in a graph database model [5]

The upper illustration shows a small portion of Twitter users represented in a graph-based database. Each node (marked as the user) corresponds to an individual and is connected by relationships that describe user interactions. As illustrated on the picture, Zoe follows Ian on Twitter, as well as Leo and Ian, but even though Zoe follows Leo, Leo hasn't (yet) reciprocated.

Neo4j is a graph database management system, implemented in Java and accessible from software written in other languages through the Cypher query language over a transactional HTTP endpoint. Headquartered in San Mateo, California, Neo4j has offices in Sweden, Germany, Singapore and in the United Kingdom. The core concept and idea of Neo4j were conceived in the early 21st century [6].

Like many other open-source projects, Neo4j also had very specific origins. Neo4j is currently the world's leading graph database. Its architecture is designed for optimal management, storage, and interpretation of nodes and relationships. Neo4j is scalable and can be deployed as a standalone server or across multiple machines in a fault-tolerant cluster in production environments. There are two main editions of Neo4j available, the Community Edition and the Enterprise Edition. The Enterprise Edition includes everything that the Community Edition offers, along with additional enterprise features such as backup capabilities, clustering, and failover support [6].

In the beginning, Neo4j was not a complete graph database management system; it was more resembled a library that developers could use in their code to facilitate working with connected data structures. It was primarily focused on creating an abstraction layer for graphs for developers. After some time, the open-source project made a radical decision to move away

from the MySQL infrastructure and introduce significant changes. The entire infrastructure, including low-level components like handling binary files, was optimized for working with graphs [7].

Neo4j is more visibly oriented towards the OLTP side of the database ecosystem. This doesn't mean that it's impossible to perform any analytical tasks with Neo4j. In fact, some analytical tasks, in the relational world, are much more efficiently executed within a graph database. In the future, there will almost certainly be additional enhancements to Neo4j that will make it even more suitable for OLAP tasks [7].

Neo4j has an upper limit on the size of graphs it can support and can handle individual graphs with tens of billions of nodes, relationships and properties. The current version of Neo4j supports approximately 34 billion nodes and relationships and around 274 billion properties. This is entirely sufficient for large-scale graphs like Facebook's, as well as similar network graph sizes. These storage limitations, in practice, do not pose any constraints because only large enterprises, such as Google, can surpass these limits and they are set for storage optimization and can be increased in future versions [7].

ArangoDB is the company behind the ArangoGraph Insights platform, a data and analytics platform that uncovers insights from challenging or impossible data using traditional SQL, document, or even other graph databases. The ArangoGraph Insights platform serves as a scalable foundation for graph analysis and complex data architectures for thousands of Fortune 500 enterprises and innovative startups across various industries, including financial services, healthcare and telecommunications. Founded in 2015 in Cologne, Germany, ArangoDB Inc. is supported by investors and data analytics companies based in San

Francisco, California, with offices and employees worldwide [8].

ArangoDB is a scalable graph database management system with a wide range of features and a rich ecosystem. It supports various data access patterns thanks to its multi-model approach, combining the analytical power of graphs with JSON documents [8].

ArangoDB is available in open-source and commercial editions and can be used for on-premises deployment as well as a fully customized cloud service through the ArangoGraph Insights platform. ArangoDB allows working with structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data equally in the form of schemas - free-form JSON objects, without the need to connect these objects to form a graph [8].

ArangoDB is designed to support multiple data models using a unified query language, AQL. ArangoDB also comes with an integrated search engine for information retrieval, such as text search with relevance ranking. ArangoDB is written in C++, built to operate at large scales, whether in the cloud or on a company's local servers [8].

ArangoDB is a multi-model database with a predominantly in-memory approach. All data is stored in persistent storage for durability. However, for efficient usage of ArangoDB, frequently accessed pages or the set of data used often (also called a working set) should fit into the main memory. At the same time, unlike most NoSQL databases, ArangoDB supports join operations and allows users to specify either multi-collection ACID transactions or standard single-document transactions to enhance performance [9].

ArangoDB's motivation is to combine the most common use cases of NoSQL databases. Other NoSQL databases that also use the JSON data format, like MongoDB for documents and Neo4j for graphs, naturally support only one data model. ArangoDB attempts to combine their use cases to build an all-in-one database, so users do not have to use a different database for various data types. The first version of ArangoDB was released in early spring in 2012 [9].

OrientDB is a multi-model NoSQL DBMS that supports graphs, documents, key-value, and object-oriented concept. Instead of merely implementing another layer with an API, OrientDB effectively integrates these models. It also supports both disk and in-memory storage. It is also an ACID-compliant DBMS capable of handling transactional workloads. OrientDB supports a multi-master distributed architecture [10].

OrientDB is an open-source database management system written in Java programming language. It supports schema-less, full-schema and mixed-schema modes. It has a robust security profiling system based on users and roles and supports queries using Gremlin along with extended SQL for graph traversal. The development of OrientDB continues to rely on an open-source community led by OrientDB LTD and the project uses GitHub for source code management and version control [11].

Ranked as the second most popular graph database according to DB Engines, OrientDB combine different models into a single engine, which makes powerful and user-friendly tool that doesn't restrict users to adopting just one database model. Originally developed by Luca Garulli in 2010, Luca transformed the existing OrientDB ODBMS platform in Java into OrientDB. In January 2018, CallidusCloud and consequently OrientDB, was acquired by SAP SE [10].

OrientDB Community Edition is free for any use (Apache 2 license). This open-source software is developed by a community of developers. Features such as horizontal scaling, fault tolerance, clustering, data sharing, and replication are not disabled in the OrientDB Community Edition. OrientDB Enterprise Edition is the commercial version of OrientDB Community Edition designed for handling more complex and demanding use cases. OrientDB Enterprise Edition includes additional features such as query profiler, distributed cluster configuration, metric logging, live monitoring, Teleporter (migration tool), and configurable notifications [11].

Table 1

Comparative view			
	Neo4j	ArangoDB	OrientDB
Pros	The most popular base and Cypher	Flexible schemes or no scheme	Various data types
	A lot of good documentation	Data sharing (sharding)	Record encryption: AES, DES
	Very good support	Multi-model	Token auth., LDAP integration
	Planning tools and backups	AQL supports JOIN operations	Hybrid scheme
	Scalability	Various data types	Multi-model
Cons	It does not support sharding	High memory usage	More effort because multiple concepts
	Expensive commercial editions	A little info for backups	Less support and smaller community
	Bugs of new functionalities	Scalability should be better	Slower queries for large graphs
	It does not support date types	Lack of built-in analytics	Existence of bugs

Results

An interesting characteristic is that all three database models support many integrations such as BigBI, Hackolade, KeyLines and ReGraph. It is worth noting that Neo4j currently has the most documentation and is currently the most popular graph database. There are many training courses, tutorials and video materials available to help better understanding of database and how it operates. It also appears that Neo4j has the best support and it is very responsive to questions and inquiries. ArangoDB often sends "deployment ready" reminder emails to its registered users.

Graph databases provide better performance, flexibility, and agility compared to non-relational databases. The conclusion is that, although they serve the same purpose, which is storing large amounts of data with many interconnected relationships, they differ significantly in the functionalities they offer.

ArangoDB provides users with the ability to use a flexible schema. ArangoDB leverages similarities in document structures to save storage space. It identifies identical document schemas and stores each unique schema only once. This process is called shaping. ArangoDB features a modern query language called AQL, which bears a strong resemblance to SQL and allows for executing complex queries and processes, giving it a significant advantage. It also has functionalities like data sharding. It is a multi-model database and operates on Azure Cloud. Information available about ArangoDB backups can be somewhat confusing, making it an area that could benefit from improvement [12].

The advantage of using ArangoDB is evident in its support for multi-model capabilities, allowing users to work with documents, graphs and key-value pairs within a single database, eliminating the need for separate systems. Additionally, it provides a schema-less data model, enabling users to evolve their data structures over time without the need for predefined schemas. The AQL allows for searching across different data models and supports joins and graph traversal operations. Working with a multi-model database and the AQL query language may require users to become familiar with different data models and query syntaxes. While ArangoDB offers flexibility by supporting multiple data models, there may be performance trade-offs compared to specialized databases dedicated to specific data models [13].

Neo4j is one of the best choices when selecting a graph database and this software has key features such as a flexible schema, a powerful query language called Cypher, backup planning, execution, and retrieval tools, two types of architecture (server mode and embedded mode), scalability and cloud readiness. Neo4j does not support data sharding, which is a major weakness of this software so far [12].

Neo4j stores data in a graph format, allowing for visualization and traversal of relationships, making it particularly suitable for applications with complex and interconnected data. Its query language, Cypher, is specially designed for graph databases and provides an intuitive and expressive syntax for querying and manipulating graph data. It's worth noting that Neo4j

offers both free versions and commercial editions, with commercial editions providing additional features and support. The commercial version can be expensive, especially for large-scale implementations or enterprise-level use. Organizations with budget constraints may face challenges when adopting the commercial version. While Neo4j is known for its performance, certain factors can impact its speed and efficiency. In specific situations, such as working with extremely large graphs or datasets that exceed available memory resources, Neo4j's in-memory storage can pose limitations. Overcoming these limitations may require memory management optimization, the use of disk storage options, or considering alternative database solutions. Although Neo4j has been in development for many years and offers a wide range of functionalities, some newer features may still be in early stages of maturity. These features may have limited documentation, fewer real-world use cases and occasional stability issues [13].

OrientDB's database can operate in a schema-less mode, but it also supports full-schema and hybrid-schema solutions. OrientDB uses Java, SQL, and Gremlin for data manipulation, supports data sharding, can be implemented in the cloud and exhibits excellent scalability when using a distributed architecture. There is not much clarity regarding how backups function [12].

One of the advantages of using OrientDB is that it allows users to model data as graphs, documents, key-value pairs, or even as a combination of these models, providing flexibility in data representation. It also ensures data consistency and integrity by supporting atomicity, consistency, isolation and durability in transactional operations. OrientDB supports multiple query languages, including the use of its SQL extensions. However, the drawbacks include the fact that OrientDB's multi-model approach and various query languages may require users to learn and understand multiple concepts and syntaxes simultaneously. While OrientDB has an active community, it may have a smaller user base compared to some other graph databases, which can result in a more limited ecosystem and community support [13].

It is noticeable that OrientDB and Neo4j share many common features (such as support for the Java language, fault tolerance through replication, and the HTTP REST protocol). Both ArangoDB and OrientDB are multi-model databases, support ACID properties and reliable server-side transactions. In contrast, Neo4j is exclusively dedicated to graphs and does not provide partitioning capabilities [14].

Both Neo4j and ArangoDB support fault tolerance through master-slave replication. They manage data storage using volatile memory and a file storage system. OrientDB and ArangoDB are both free databases licensed under Apache 2. However, Neo4j offers a commercial edition under the APGL license in addition to the free version [14].

Both Neo4j and OrientDB are dedicated to supporting the storage of large graph-based datasets. This ensures scalability and performance when inserting or querying data. The primary difference

between these two NoSQL databases lies in their underlying storage. Specifically, while OrientDB is primarily based on documents as its main storage (with an additional graph layer supporting graphs), Neo4j is based on graphs as its primary storage [14].

Unlike OrientDB, which supports a wide range of data types, Neo4j only supports primitive types. With Neo4j, precision is lost when storing decimal numbers (amounts, currencies, salaries, etc.). While OrientDB supports "date" and "date and time" types for easy date management, Neo4j, on the other hand, does not support date data types. Therefore, users have to manage date and time data differently. OrientDB also supports other complex types, such as a binary type for storing binary large objects (BLOBs), an embedded type for recursively storing embedded objects, collections, and maps. ArangoDB supports JSON data types, including numbers, UTF-8 strings, boolean values, arrays/lists, and documents.

Neo4j supports replication, but only in the Enterprise version. In both databases, Neo4j and ArangoDB, the replication mechanism is based on the master/slave architecture. This means that only one server can be the master. Therefore, Neo4j and ArangoDB are not able to scale by write operations because the throughput of these operations is limited by the capacity of a single master server. This type of replication allows scalability by read operations and supports creating backups [14].

Unlike Neo4j and ArangoDB, which support master/slave replication, OrientDB supports replication with multiple master servers and a schema-less architecture. This feature ensures data reliability. This means that all servers in the cluster are masters and capable of reading from and writing to the database. Indeed, in OrientDB, throughput is not limited by a single server [14].

OrientDB can host multiple databases per instance. In contrast, Neo4j allows only one database per server. With ArangoDB, it is possible to connect multiple secondary databases to the primary database. ArangoDB provides asynchronous replication and allows both vertical and horizontal sharding [14].

The operational database manages space without need for restart or maintenance interruption. When records are deleted, OrientDB has the advantage of automatically reusing the freed space. This is done transparently while the server is online. In contrast, Neo4j cannot automatically reclaim space from deleted records. To utilize the freed space, Neo4j requires a full server restart [14].

OrientDB supports basic security management based on the user and role model. It also supports secure SSL connections starting from version 1.7. Additionally, OrientDB offers the option to encrypt records on disk using AES or DES algorithms (starting from version 2.2). Encryption can be configured to operate at the cluster level or the database level. Furthermore, OrientDB supports token-based authentication and LDAP integration. Since OrientDB supports multiple master node replication, it is possible to replicate server databases within the cluster. This represents another security solution by reducing the

risk of data loss and downtime while increasing data availability [14].

Discussion

Relational database models have successfully been the primary choice for storage models in the last fifty years. They excel at representing relatively linear data where relationships are not too complex. With the rise of the web and semi-structured data, highly interconnected and complex data have become increasingly prevalent in the technology world. Relational models have failed to adequately represent highly interconnected data, leading to the need for new database models.

Graph models have particularly demonstrated their advantages in specific domains such as the web, social networks, and transportation infrastructure. Various technology companies and independent researchers have developed their implementations of graph databases, such as Neo4j, ArangoDB, and OrientDB. Graph database technologies have significantly contributed to the growth of science and technology and will continue to do so in the foreseeable future.

NoSQL is generally a complementary solution for addressing scalability, complexity and performance-related issues. Non-relational databases offer many improvements over traditional relational databases, such as greater scalability across regular servers or instances. They also do not adhere to strict data insertion schemas and therefore can more easily accommodate various data types with minimal schema-level changes.

Graph database systems are designed to model and explore data relationships in a way that is not efficiently achievable in other types of database management systems. The need for a graph data model often arises from use cases such as social network analysis, identity and access management, recommendations for online products and services, network and device management, as well as detecting financial fraud in banking and insurance companies.

In general, the use of relational databases has remained quite stable recently. All other categories of databases have gained popularity, while the usage of graph database systems has increased by more than 500 percent. It's important to note that relational databases are still much more popular than any other type of database, constituting 82% of the total popularity score of all systems listed on DB-Engines and 7 out of the top 10 systems in the current rankings are relational systems [15].

The database landscape is quite extensive, and there appears to be a growing demand for all categories of database management systems. However, it's interesting to note that graph database systems are attracting an increasing share of attention from development teams within organizations.

In general, graph-based databases perform better with complex data during searches, especially in terms of traversing relationships. It is always recommended to use graph databases for more intricate and interrelated data. In other words, if queries are expected

to involve data from multiple tables, using graph databases with appropriate relationship orientations is advisable.

After all that has been presented in this paper, it is important to conclude that Neo4j and ArangoDB stand out for their functionalities and are the best options for graph databases in today's world. Neo4j is optimized for graph-based databases, while ArangoDB and OrientDB are suitable for databases with various data models (graphs, documents, key-value). However, it is still concluded that Neo4j is the superior software with enhanced implemented features compared to ArangoDB.

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